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3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable examines political economy barriers to climate policy through sectoral entry points that can make transitions more just, feasible, and development-compatible. It focuses on three areas where governance and politics strongly shape outcomes: coal transition strategies, carbon pricing, and international finance. Across these domains, the report draws on seven peer-reviewed studies and working papers to highlight five strategic entry points: i) decentralized just transition planning, ii) clean industrial development, iii) revenue recycling with social protection, iv) strategic framing and coalition building for carbon taxes, and v) equity-focused international finance reforms. Coal transitions are shown to depend on domestic contexts. Comparative analysis of 12 coal-relevant countries reveals six distinct clusters of political economy dynamics, ranging from civil society-driven transition in South Africa to contested transition pathways in India and Indonesia. Case studies stress the need for regionally tailored approaches. Carbon pricing is politically viable when embedded in broader fiscal or political agendas. Evidence from 46 global policy attempts underlines the role of coalitions, leadership, and framing co-benefits. Microsimulations for 16 Latin American and Caribbean countries show regressive impacts, with many highly affected households lacking social protection. The international finance analysis assesses the G7 pledge and Clean Energy Transition Partnership, tracking shifts in public finance for energy across income groups. While fossil fuel support has declined, clean energy funding has not risen proportionally, remains loan-heavy, and is concentrated in wealthier nations. Low-income countries receive negligible concessional flows, while G7 members continue expanding domestic fossil infrastructure. The study recommends embedding distributive justice into finance governance, scaling grant-based clean energy support for the Global South and aligning domestic actions with international commitments.

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See report below.

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1. Introduction

This report analyses barriers to sectoral entry points, defined as strategic opportunities within energy, finance, industry, international policy, and institutions that can catalyse decarbonisation while addressing local political economy constraints. At present, there are several gaps in the literature on sectoral entry points. First, evidence remains fragmented and skewed toward energy supply and carbon pricing in high-income settings, with limited comparative assessments across sectors and governance levels. Second, guidance on sequencing, coalition-building, and policy durability is often inferred from case narratives rather than evaluated with longitudinal or quasi-experimental methods (Meckling et al. 2015; Aklin and Urpelainen 2018; Gallagher 2017). Third, Global South contexts – especially subnational politics, state-owned enterprises, and informal labour markets – are under-represented in understanding sectoral entry points. Finally, mainstream pathways and modelling studies still weakly integrate political-economy dynamics such as distributional impacts, and administrative capacity, limiting their usefulness for identifying feasible entry points (Peng et al. 2021).

This synthesises evidence on sectoral entry points from five peer-reviewed publications and two working papers produced under this deliverable. Table 1 below summarises the seven studies, outlining their sectoral scope, governance level, political economy constraints, and identified entry points.

From these studies, we identify five strategic entry points for advancing just, politically feasible, and development-compatible climate action. The first group – coal transition strategies – includes (1) decentralised just transition planning and (2) clean industrial development. The second group – carbon pricing and fiscal reform – focuses on (3) revenue recycling with social protection and (4) strategic coalition building. The third group on international energy finance governance focuses on (5) equity-focused reform of international public finance for energy.

The studies focus on the energy sector, carbon pricing as a cross-sectoral policy instrument, and international energy finance because of their outsized role in climate policy debates and the political economy challenges they present. The energy sector accounts for the largest share of emissions worldwide and is central to economic activity, making its transformation essential to meeting climate targets and enabling low carbon transitions in other sectors (IPCC 2022; IEA 2025; Sovacool et al. 2025). Within the energy sector, we focus especially on coal-power generation due to its central role in electricity generation and industrial energy use in many economies. Coal is the most carbon-intensive fossil fuel and is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC 2022). At the same time, it underpins energy security, industrial competitiveness, and employment and is deeply embedded in

political and economic systems, making its phase-out a highly complex and politically sensitive process (Jakob and Steckel 2022). Understanding the barriers to coal transitions is essential to identifying viable entry points for deep decarbonisation.

To explore barriers to coal phase out, Manych et. al (2023) apply the Actors, Objectives, Context (AOC) framework (Jakob and Steckel 2022; Jakob et al. 2020) to classify 12 coal-relevant countries – Germany, UK, Chile, Colombia, United States, Kenya, South Africa, Indonesia, India, Vietnam, Philippines, and Pakistan – into six political economy clusters. These clusters reflect differences in governance structures, market dynamics, and societal influence on coal transitions.

Two case studies deepen this analysis. The first examines political economy challenges across states and regions in India's energy transition (Ordonez et. al 2023). It highlights how subnational dynamics, governance structures, and regional dependencies on coal create both barriers and opportunities for change. The second explores coal-fired power plants and industrial development in Indonesia, where coal's role in powering large firms complicates the path towards a low-carbon energy system (Missbach et al. 2025). These case studies illustrate the ways in which national and subnational political economies interact to shape sectoral transitions.

Carbon pricing is widely recognised as a cost-effective mechanism to drive emissions reductions. However, its adoption and durability depend on political and social conditions, including public acceptance, distributional impacts, and the ability to align such policies with broader development objectives (Stiglitz et al. 2017; Klenert et al. 2018; Levi et al. 2020; Ohlendorf et al. 2021). In this report, Missbach et al. (2024) and Klein et al (2025) examine the adoption, design, and public support for carbon pricing across varying political and socio-economic contexts. Evidence from 16 Latin American and Caribbean countries, suggest that carbon pricing tends to be regressive, with greater inequality within income groups than between them (Missbach et al. 2024). Many highly affected households lack social protection, underscoring the need for targeted transfers, in-kind support, or public goods investment to address these disparities. A review of 46 policy attempts in 35 jurisdictions shows that carbon taxes are rarely adopted on environmental grounds alone; rather fiscal and political objectives dominate (Klein et al. 2025). Further, adoption depends on political leadership, coalition-building, and overcoming opposition from industrial lobbies. Based on these findings six political economy profiles are identified influencing adoption, with lessons on coalition-building, policy framing, and revenue recycling strategies that enhance political feasibility and public trust.

International public finance is a key driver of energy transitions, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where access to concessional finance and investment flows can determine the feasibility and pace of decarbonisation (Patt et al. 2022). Jaiswal

and Chatterjee (2025) critically assess the implementation of the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) and the G7 commitment to phase out international public finance for fossil fuels. The analysis foregrounds the geopolitical and distributive justice dimensions of these finance shifts and their implications for the Global South. It underscores the importance of addressing equity and capacity differences in the design of climate finance and international policy frameworks.

Taken together, these papers span three interconnected levels of governance – regional, national, and international – that shape sectoral entry points, coal transition pathways, and the political feasibility of instruments such as carbon pricing and taxes. At the regional level, they explore subnational political economies, such as state-level governance in India, where energy transitions and the distributional impacts of carbon taxes are influenced by local economic dependencies, political coalitions, and institutional capacities. At the national level, the studies analyse how domestic policy frameworks, industrial strategies, and stakeholder interests determine the feasibility of low-carbon shifts, including the adoption and design of carbon pricing mechanisms. At the international level, they assess the role of transnational drivers such as international public finance in shaping incentives and constraints for just energy transitions. This multi-scalar perspective underscores that sectoral entry points need to take into account the interactions between these levels of governance. Currently integrated assessment models face challenges in accounting for such political economy and multi-scalar dynamics (Peng et al. 2021).

Table 1. Political Economy of Sectoral Entry Points

Reference	Sector	Sub-sector	Governance Level	Country / Country Group	Key Findings on Political Economy Constraints	Sectoral Entry Points
1 Manych et al. (2023) published in <i>Energy Research and Social Sciences</i>	Energy	Power Generation and Industrial use	National(comparative)	Uses topic modelling to classify 12 coal-relevant countries into four clusters reflecting their coal transition political economy. (AOC Framework)	Framing of coal phase-out varies: civil society and legal pressure in some (Kenya, SA), market-based exits in others (UK, USA), and contested transitions in India and Indonesia.	Tailor phase-out strategies to domestic discourse and framing; support narrative shifts through civic engagement and communication.
2 Ordonez et al. (2023) published in <i>Energy Policy</i>	Energy	Power Generation and Industrial use	Regional	Subnational grouping in India based on coal dependency and institutional capacity contrast.	Coal-dependent states face higher socio-economic transition risks and weaker state capacity to manage transitions.	Subnational compensation schemes; regional retraining programs and fiscal transfer mechanisms.
3 Missbach et al. (2025) Working Paper	Energy	Power	National	Individual country case study (Indonesia)	Coal-fired power plants improved reliability and industrial performance for large firms but had adverse effects on SMEs.	Differentiate support for SMEs vs. large industry.
4 Jaiswal & Chatterjee (2025) Accepted for publication in <i>Global Environmental Politics</i>	Energy	International Public Finance for energy projects	International	Global South, G7	CETP and G7 climate finance commitments are uneven. Fossil fuel finance declined but clean finance has not risen equivalently, disadvantaging low-income countries.	Reform international finance governance to include CBDR-RC and distributive justice; increase concessional flows.

5	Klein et al. (2025) Working Paper	Cross-Sectoral (Carbon taxation)	—	National(comparative)	6 distinct country clusters or political economy landscapes identified based on systematic review of 46 policy attempts for carbon taxation across varied political systems. These clusters are based on institutional configurations, actor dynamics, and the objectives behind carbon pricing policies. (AOC framework)	Carbon pricing adoption depends on political systems and interest group dynamics: corporatist countries adopt more easily, while fossil-dependent economies face strong business and public opposition. Carbon taxes are rarely purely environmental—fiscal and political goals dominate. Public support rises when revenues fund visible, fair outcomes like health or clean energy	Enable coalition-building; align carbon pricing with social policy timing and transparency.
6	Missbach et al. (2024) published in <i>World Development</i>	Cross-Sectoral (Carbon pricing)		National(comparative)	Uses comparative microsimulation to analyze 16 Latin American countries, focusing on how carbon pricing impacts households across different socio-economic groups. Differentiate countries by socio-political capacity to absorb carbon pricing impact	Carbon pricing is regressive, especially for unprotected households; horizontal inequalities, or disparities within income groups, are found to be more pronounced than vertical inequalities across income levels. Existing social protection programs do not reach many of the households most adversely impacted by carbon pricing.	Integrate carbon pricing with social protection reforms; target horizontal inequality dimensions.
7	Mohammadzadeh et al. (2024) published in npj <i>Climate Action</i>	Cross-cutting (Carbon Pricing)		National(comparative)	Empirically identified through systematic review groupings of countries based on how public support for carbon pricing varies	Green spending is more popular than direct cash transfers; targeted cash transfers and environmentally focused	Link fiscal instruments to visible green investments; link carbon revenues to social protection,

across different revenue recycling strategies. (26 countries)

public spending are more effective—both socially and politically—than uniform per capita transfers, which may fail to provide adequate support to the most vulnerable population

expanding the reach of cash transfer systems to households currently outside the net

The remainder of the report is structured as follows. **Section 2** maps sectoral entry points for climate policy, grouping them into coal transition strategies, carbon pricing and fiscal reform, and international energy finance governance. The sections that follow deep dive into the peer-reviewed articles and working papers informing these sectoral entry points. **Section 3** applies the AOC framework to classify political economy conditions for coal phase-out across 12 countries and presents detailed case studies of India and Indonesia. **Section 4** examines the political economy barriers to carbon pricing, including household-level impacts and policy adoption dynamics. **Section 5** analyses equity gaps in G7 international public finance for energy, focusing on CETP implementation. The conclusion synthesises these findings, emphasising the need for context-sensitive, equitable, and politically strategic approaches. It recommends developing stylised political economy indicators for integration into climate–economy models. This can enable scenario analysis that reflects real-world governance and institutional constraints.

2. Mapping Sectoral Entry Points for Climate Policy

We identify five sectoral entry points – strategic leverage areas within and across sectors – that can guide just, politically feasible, and development-compatible climate policy. The sectoral entry points are designed to align national decarbonization efforts with broader social and economic priorities.

Each entry point is informed by peer-reviewed articles and working papers produced under this deliverable which are grouped into three themes – political economy of coal transition strategies (Section 3), political economy of carbon pricing and fiscal reform (Section 4) and international energy finance (Section 5) and discussed under individual sections.

2.1. Entry Points for Coal Transition Strategies

Decentralized Just Transition Planning

This entry point focuses on managing the social and economic consequences of moving away from coal in ways that reflect local conditions. Effective transitions account for differences in regional economies, employment patterns, and fiscal dependencies. Policies should be tailored to specific states or provinces, create pathways for alternative industries, and ensure local actors are engaged in decision-making.

Evidence from Manych et al. (2023) shows that in India, Indonesia, and the Philippines, coal remains politically resilient because it is viewed as essential for low-cost electricity, energy security, and domestic development. By contrast, South Africa and

Kenya illustrate how strong civil society participation can challenge coal dominance, leading to legal challenges and coal project cancellations. Ordonez et al. (2023) further highlight India's state-level variations: coal-producing states rely heavily on royalties and jobs, while more industrialized states are advancing with renewables, creating political asymmetries that complicate national policy.

Clean Industrial Development Policy

Reframing industrial competitiveness around low-carbon growth is critical in coal-dependent industrial economies. Without a compelling clean energy alternative, industrial policy risks locking in fossil dependence. A more sustainable approach pairs targeted investment in renewable or low-carbon energy infrastructure with reliable grid access for industrial zones, while ensuring that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) share in the benefits.

Missbach et al. (2025) show that in Indonesia, coal plant commissioning boosted output and jobs in large manufacturing firms through improved electricity reliability and transport links but left SMEs disadvantaged—sometimes due to increased labor competition. This suggests that without deliberate policy design, the economic gains from energy investment will remain concentrated in capital-intensive sectors.

2.2. Entry points for Carbon Pricing and Fiscal Reform

Revenue Recycling and Social Protection in Carbon Pricing

This entry point addresses political resistance to carbon pricing by tackling its distributional consequences. Carbon pricing becomes more politically viable when revenues are recycled in ways that protect vulnerable households and visibly fund public goods. Expanding social protection coverage, particularly to excluded households, and investing in green infrastructure that benefits a wide range of constituencies are key steps. Transparent communication on revenue use can further strengthen public trust.

Missbach et al. (2024) find that in Latin America and the Caribbean, carbon pricing is regressive in most countries, disproportionately affecting low-income households, with many of those households excluded from social protection schemes.

Mohammadzadeh Valencia et al. (2024) show that targeted cash transfers and green public investments are both socially equitable and politically advantageous, outperforming uniform per capita transfers in reaching the most vulnerable.

Strategic Framing and Coalition Building for Carbon Taxes

The design and adoption of carbon taxes depend on political institutions, framing, and coalition-building. Successful approaches involve inclusive public consultations, clear

public messaging about revenue use, and framing policies in terms of co-benefits such as job creation, health, and equity.

Klein et al. (2025) provide evidence that consensual and corporatist political systems, such as those in Scandinavia, are more likely to sustain carbon pricing, whereas fossil-heavy economies face entrenched opposition from industry lobbies and concerned publics. Public support rises when revenues are used for visible, socially beneficial outcomes rather than absorbed into general budgets.

2.3. Entry point for International Finance Governance

Redesigning International Finance Governance with Equity

Global supply-side climate governance must be restructured to avoid placing disproportionate burdens on low-income countries. Restricting fossil fuel finance is necessary, but it should be matched by scaled-up, accessible funding for clean energy, particularly in the Global South. Equity-oriented governance should integrate the principle of “Common But Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities” (CBDR-RC), expand concessional finance, and provide technical assistance for clean infrastructure deployment.

Jaiswal and Chatterjee (2025) show that while initiatives like the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) and complementary commitments by G7 have successfully reduced the flow of international public finance for fossil fuel. However, they have not resulted in proportional increases in clean energy funding. Most of the benefits accrue to high-income countries, while low-income nations are largely excluded. This imbalance raises concerns about fairness of the policy. Without consistent and reciprocal action from G7 to scale down their own fossil infrastructure, the legitimacy of international climate policy risks being undermined - particularly in the eyes of developing nations that are being asked to forgo similar investments essential for their development.

3. Classification of Political Economy Factors: Country Groupings and Case Studies of Coal Transitions

In this section, we examine the political economy factors shaping coal transitions through two complementary lenses: a cross-country analysis that groups nations with similar structural and institutional characteristics to reveal broad patterns, and country case studies that provide detailed insight into how these dynamics unfold in specific contexts.

3.1. The political economy of coal across 12 countries

Manych et al. (2023) examine how political economy factors shape the persistence of coal across different national contexts and test whether computational text analysis can complement traditional qualitative approaches. They apply topic modelling (TM) – specifically Latent Dirichlet Allocation – to 212 semi-structured expert interviews carried out between 2018 and 2021 from 12 coal-relevant countries that together account for about 30 % of global coal capacity. All interviews follow the Actors-Objectives-Context (AOC) framework. This framework works by identifying key actors (such as political leaders, business interests, NGOs, the public, and technocrats), their stated or inferred objectives (e.g. economic growth, environmental goals, signalling, competitiveness concerns), and the broader context in which policy debates unfold (including political institutions, economic crises, legal barriers, and cultural discourses).

TM detects 22 latent topics, which they group into four thematic categories—Actors and Interests, Electric Power System, Energy Governance and Markets, and Policies.

Results show that while most topics recur across actor groups, emphases differ. **Economic actors** highlight markets, finance, and infrastructure. **Political actors** focus on policy content and **societal actors**, particularly national ones, stress stakeholders and vested interests. Six country clusters emerge from the analysis (Figure 1). The policy-driven phase-out cluster, comprising of Germany and the UK, focuses heavily on coal exit policies and governance frameworks. The governance of fossil fuel markets cluster, comprising of Chile and Colombia, centres on coordination between political, societal, and private actors in fossil fuel pricing, mining, and regulation. The market-driven phase-out cluster, represented by the United States, emphasises the electricity mix and coal's decline through price and competitiveness pressures. The civil society cluster – Kenya and South Africa – highlights grassroots and advocacy groups that shape coal debates and challenge projects. The electricity mix and tariffs cluster, composed of Indonesia and India, concentrates on energy pricing, subsidies, and vested interests tied to mining and generation. Finally, the energy sector planning cluster with Vietnam, the Philippines, and Pakistan, focuses on government planning, power development plans, and the influence of private and political actors on long-term strategies.

Manych et al. (2023) conclude that TM yields results broadly consistent with traditional qualitative content analysis, while offering greater scalability, comparability, and a direct link from raw text to cross-country patterns. The identified clusters provide a basis for policy learning, enabling countries with similar political economy conditions to draw on each other's transition experiences.

Figure 1. Hierarchical clustering of countries. Countries are grouped based on their topic distributions. The tree is cut at the grey line, resulting in 6 country clusters. *Source Manych et. al (2023).*

3.2. Country Case Studies

Political Economy challenges across states and regions in India's energy transition

Ordonez et al. (2023), examines the regional disparities in India's political economy of coal phase-out. Using microsimulation combined with input–output modelling, the study analyses how different states are variably exposed to the economic and social consequences of a transition away from coal (Figure 2).

The findings reveal that Eastern states such as Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, and Odisha are particularly vulnerable due to their heavy reliance on coal for employment and fiscal revenues (Figure 2). In contrast, Western and central states are better positioned to benefit from the growth of renewable energy industries, both in terms of investment flows and job creation. The analysis also shows that vulnerable populations—those with limited access to alternative livelihoods—are disproportionately located in coal-dependent regions, intensifying the political risks associated with transition policies.

Ordonez et al. emphasize that without carefully designed compensatory measures, such as regional transition funds or targeted revenue recycling, climate policy interventions risk deepening existing interstate inequalities. This underscores the importance of geographically differentiated transition planning that accounts for the uneven distribution of both costs and benefits.

Figure 2. Qualitative assessment of disadvantageous (negative scale) and favorable (positive scale) conditions as a result of an energy transition across Indian states. Red markers show net effects over all dimensions. Numeric values 1, 2 and 3 correspond to low, medium or high effects, depending on the tercile of impacts in which the respective state is located (own elaboration). Source: Ordonez et. al 2023. For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.

Coal-fired power plants and industrial development in Indonesia

Missbach et al. (2025) use the commissioning of coal-fired power plants in Indonesia between 1984 and 2015 as a case study to examine how fossil-fuel infrastructure shapes industrial development. Using high-resolution firm-level data and a quasi-experimental research design, the study assesses the causal effects of coal plant operations on local manufacturing firms. The results in Table 2 show that while average effects across all firms were modest, the benefits were highly uneven. Larger and more capital-intensive firms (more than 250 employees) experienced significant gains in employment, inputs, outputs, and value added in the four years following the commissioning of nearby coal plants. Medium-sized firms also showed improvements, though to a lesser extent. In contrast, smaller firms (fewer than 100 employees) not only failed to benefit but actually experienced a decline in employment, suggesting negative spillovers from increased competition for labour and possibly higher input prices.

These heterogeneous effects were shaped by improved electricity reliability, increased firm entry, and modest enhancements in transportation infrastructure. Larger firms were better positioned to capitalize on more stable grid access, while smaller firms were more vulnerable to rising wages and market competition. Interestingly, coal-fired plants had stronger positive impacts than gas, hydro, or geothermal alternatives, underlining coal's effectiveness in delivering concentrated, reliable energy in infrastructure-constrained environments.

This case underscores how coal infrastructure has functioned as a form of industrial policy, selectively enabling growth among specific firm types and sectors. It highlights the political economy complexities of phasing out coal, as the firms that benefit are often economically and politically influential. The findings emphasize the need for just transition strategies that account for firm heterogeneity and regional disparities. Replacing coal with clean energy will require not only technological solutions but also institutional and economic planning to ensure inclusive industrial development.

Table 2. Effects of coal-red power plant commissioning on employment, outputs, inputs, and value added, differentiated by firm size

Dependent variable	Labor (1)	Input (2)	Output (3)	Value added (4)
<i>Variable</i>				
Treatment group*POST (Smaller firms)	-0.021** (0.009)	-0.027 (0.022)	-0.028 (0.019)	-0.032* (0.018)
Treatment group*POST (Medium-size firms)	0.035** (0.016)	0.096*** (0.033)	0.064** (0.029)	0.023 (0.031)
Treatment group*POST (Larger firms)	0.076*** (0.017)	0.097*** (0.031)	0.106*** (0.027)	0.100*** (0.029)
<i>Fixed effects</i>				
Firm-firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Event time-cohort-firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Treatment group-cohort-firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry-year-firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Island-year-firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year t = 0 -firm group-FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	868,518	831,474	835,532	868,470
R ²	0.93	0.90	0.92	0.90

This table reports OLS estimates of the effect of coal-fired power plant commissioning on the performance of incumbent and local manufacturing firms, differentiated by firm size one year before the treatment. The outcome variables are labor demand (1) (in log total employees), total material inputs (2), total outputs (3), and value added (4) (all in log IDR). This table reports estimates and standard errors (in parentheses) clustered at the village level where the treatment is assigned. The unit of observation is an Indonesian manufacturing firms for which we have annual observations. We assign firm-year observations to the treatment or control group for each cohort year. We stack different cohorts with respect to event time. We exclude firms from our sample if they are located in villages that were never treated. We assign firms to firm groups for each cohort according to the number of employees one year prior to the treatment. Smaller firms are those with less than 100 employees. Medium-size firms are those with more than 99 and less than 250 employees. Larger firms are those with more than 249 employees. Note that we effectively remove firms from cohorts with missing information on employment in the year before the treatment year. All estimations include a set of fixed effects. Significance levels are: *: $p < 0.1$; **: $p < 0.05$; ***: $p < 0.01$. Source Missbach et al 2025.

Discussion on entry points

The comparative analysis of 12 coal-relevant countries and the case studies on India and Indonesia highlight how coal transitions are deeply conditioned by national and subnational political economies. Together, the findings underscore the importance of decentralised just transition planning and clean industrial development as entry points for climate policy. In practice, this means tailoring coal phase-out strategies to local

contexts, compensating coal-dependent regions, and ensuring that new clean energy investments foster inclusive industrial opportunities. Without these measures, transitions risk reinforcing inequality and entrenching opposition from powerful industrial actors. By embedding distributive justice and regional differentiation into transition planning, coal phase-out can become politically feasible and development-compatible.

4. Political Economy Barriers and Policy Options for Carbon Pricing

In this section, we examine the political economy factors shaping carbon pricing through two separate case studies: an empirical analysis of household-level impacts in 16 Latin American and Caribbean countries, and a global review of 46 policy attempts in 35 jurisdictions. The first case study assesses how carbon pricing affects different income groups and evaluates the effectiveness of existing social protection in mitigating regressive impacts. The second investigates the political, institutional, and coalition-building conditions that influence the adoption, design, and durability of carbon pricing reforms across diverse contexts.

4.1. Cash transfers in the context of carbon pricing reforms in Latin America and the Caribbean

Missbach et al (2024) examine the extent to which existing cash transfer programs in 16 Latin American and Caribbean countries can alleviate the negative distributional impacts of carbon pricing on households. Carbon pricing, while efficient for reducing emissions, can disproportionately affect low-income and vulnerable households by raising the costs of essential goods and services. Using nationally representative household survey data, combined with multi-regional input–output modelling, ¹Missbach et al. (2024) simulate the effects of a carbon price of USD 40 per ton of CO₂. This approach allows them to assess which households are most impacted and whether those households are currently covered by government transfer programs.

The analysis reveals that carbon pricing is regressive in 11 of the 16 countries studied. Lower-income households tend to face a higher cost burden relative to their total expenditures. However, the study finds that differences in carbon pricing impacts within income groups (horizontal inequality) are often larger than differences between

¹ Input–output modeling is a quantitative analytical framework, which represents the inter-industry transactions within an economy through a system of linear equations. In this model, each sector's output is simultaneously considered as an input to other sectors, thereby capturing the structural interdependencies across the economy. The framework is commonly expressed in matrix form, facilitating the examination of how exogenous changes in final demand affect production, income, and employment levels throughout the system

income groups (vertical inequality). This indicates that even within poor or rich households, there is significant variation in how carbon pricing affects them, challenging the effectiveness of average-based compensation mechanisms.

Key factors associated with higher household costs include car ownership, cooking fuel choices (especially reliance on LPG), and electricity use. Yet, many of the households that bear the highest costs are not necessarily the poorest and are often excluded from existing cash transfer programs. In some countries, such as Paraguay and El Salvador, large portions of the most affected households receive no government support at all.

The findings highlight the importance of assessing climate policy instruments, such as carbon pricing, within the framework of broader policy packages. Fiscal revenues generated by carbon pricing can be used by governments to offset excessive additional costs for households. Leveraging existing transfer programs offers practical advantages, as these do not require major institutional changes and are generally well integrated into governmental operations and familiar to citizens across Latin America and the Caribbean.

However, current cash transfer systems may provide imperfect compensation. While lump-sum transfers can reduce vertical inequality and targeted transfers address horizontal inequality, many programs fail to adequately reach poor households. This limitation highlights the potential need for reforms that expand coverage or introduce new, more tailored mechanisms. However, broadening programs poses challenges, including institutional constraints, information gaps, application costs, and social stigma.

Debates also persist on how best to integrate environmental externalities into existing tax systems. One option is to use revenues to reduce distortionary taxes, such as labour taxes. This could be valuable in economies with high informality, since carbon pricing is harder to evade. Still, reductions in labour or capital taxes may worsen inequality, as wealthier households benefit disproportionately. Alternative measures include lowering excise taxes on essential goods, which would improve progressivity given the spending patterns of low-income households.

In-kind transfers and targeted subsidies present further avenues. For example, policies that expand public transport or support clean cooking technologies could reduce fossil fuel dependence, though infrastructure improvements require time to deliver relief. Ultimately, which households face disproportionate costs varies by country.

While the scope of this study does not extend to prescribing specific complementary instruments for individual countries, Table 3 outlines general policy channels that could help alleviate cost burdens for the most affected households. This framework

may also inform future research efforts, such as evaluating the implications of exempting certain fuels from carbon pricing on overall policy efficiency, effectiveness, and fairness—particularly in contexts where fuel use for cooking or private transportation constitutes a major source of additional household costs.

Table 3. Stylized channels to compensate households with high carbon pricing incidence

Compensating those households for excessive costs which	Countries where this is relevant	Examples of instruments to be considered in further research
... are relatively poor?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Argentina • Bolivia • Brazil • Colombia • Chile • Ecuador 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lump-sum transfers • Expansion of coverage of existing transfer programs • Subsidies on subsistence consumption goods, such as food, water or housing • In-kind transfers (food, water, health goods and services)
... are relatively rich?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nicaragua 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of labor or income taxes • Reduction of contributions to health insurance or contributions to pensions
... own (and) use a car?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barbados • Brazil • Costa Rica • Dominican Republic • Ecuador • Guatemala • Mexico • Uruguay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vouchers for transport fuels • Investments in public transport infrastructure • Subsidies on electric vehicles • Exemption of transport fuels from carbon price • Targeted compensation for car owners (and users), e.g., through vehicle tax
... use LPG?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mexico • Paraguay • Peru 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vouchers for LPG • Exemption of LPG from carbon price • Subsidies on electric cookstoves
... live in rural/urban areas?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brazil • Uruguay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of local public goods (health, education, water) • Setup of (geographically) targeted transfer programs
... use electricity?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bolivia • Guatemala 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies on electricity prices for consumers • Introduction of block tariffs • Incentives for energy efficiency improvements
... identify as ethnic minority?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nicaragua • Peru 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setup of targeted transfer programs
... do not have access to established transfer programs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • El Salvador • Guatemala • Paraguay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion coverage of existing programs • Setup of targeted transfer programs

This table shows a selection of stylized instruments that governments could use to compensate households who face exceptionally high additional costs from carbon pricing. This table hinges on the assumption that governments are primarily concerned about additional costs to households. It neglects other opportunities such as green fiscal spending or reimbursing industries.

4.2. The politics of carbon taxes: determinants of successful policy adoption

Klein et al. (2025) offer a comprehensive and systematic examination of why carbon taxes succeed or fail politically. Drawing on a novel synthesis of the case study literature, they identify and analyse 82 peer-reviewed academic studies covering 46 policy attempts across 35 jurisdictions. These cases span both national and subnational levels and cover a wide geographic range, although with a clear bias toward high-income countries in Europe, North America, and Australia.

Methodologically, the study applies the Actors-Objectives-Context (AOC) framework to conduct a structured qualitative review. The study is based on a systematic literature search using a detailed search string across SCOPUS and Web of Science, combined with machine-learning-assisted screening. Ultimately, the team extracted and coded 2,966 qualitative data points and used k-means clustering to identify recurring “political economy profiles” that reflect distinct combinations of actors, motives, and contexts influencing carbon tax adoption outcomes.

The analysis reveals that carbon taxes are rarely adopted purely on environmental grounds. Instead, they are typically embedded within broader agendas of fiscal reform, economic signalling, or political strategy. Political actors – particularly ministries of finance and environment – are the most consistently influential in enabling or blocking adoption. Business actors are primarily obstructive, especially in fossil-intensive sectors, while NGOs and technocratic institutions tend to be supportive. Surprisingly, the public plays a limited and inconsistent role in most case studies, suggesting a gap in democratic engagement on this issue.

Klein et al. (2025) identify six distinct clusters of political economy configurations (Table 4). Some cases, such as those in Finland, South Africa, and Ireland, are marked by economic and climate synergies, where carbon taxes are framed as tools for both environmental protection and fiscal reform. Other successful cases arise in response to fiscal crises, especially during the post-2008 financial downturn, where revenue needs override opposition. A third group involves the crafting of coalitions, where political support is built across different stakeholder groups, often at the cost of reduced policy stringency. Conversely, institutional barriers – such as constitutional veto points, fragmented governance, or legal rulings – explain several cases where carbon taxes failed or were replaced with emissions trading schemes. In countries like Taiwan and Korea, industrial opposition successfully derailed carbon tax proposals. Finally, a set of cases (including Malaysia and Ukraine) is classified as having research gaps, due to sparse scholarly attention and limited publicly available information.

The study advances several policy recommendations based on distinct political economy profiles that face specific barriers to carbon tax adoption. In some cases,

adverse economic conditions – such as fiscal pressure or unemployment – can create opportunities when carbon taxes are framed to meet both budgetary and environmental goals. Successful adoption often depends on strong collaboration between finance and environment ministries and on a public discourse supportive of climate action.

Institutional barriers may be addressed through careful policy design, exploring alternative governance levels, or shifting to emissions trading systems, as seen in the EU. Weak coordination between agencies can be mitigated by expert task forces that strengthen policy implementation.

Organised industrial lobbies represent the strongest opposition, often invoking competitiveness, growth, and employment concerns to sway public opinion. Carbon taxes have advanced only when robust pro-tax coalitions countered this influence, usually with compromises on tax stringency.

Ultimately, political actors are decisive, while economic actors consistently resist and civil society remains fragmented. External factors—such as international agreements, economic crises, or OECD accession—can open windows of opportunity, providing incentives that help overcome domestic resistance to carbon taxation.

Table 4. Country clusters for political feasibility analysis of carbon taxation policy

Cluster	Policy cases
A: Synergies between Economic & Climate Goals	Finland (1990), Sweden (1991), Denmark (1992), Estonia (2000), Ireland (2002), Argentina (2017), South Africa (2019), Uruguay (2022)
B: Crafting Coalitions	United Kingdom (2001), British Columbia (2008), Canada (2008), Australia (2012, 2014), Mexico (2013), Japan (2012), Germany (1999)
C: Institutional Barriers	European Union (1992), Slovenia (1997), France (1999, 2008), California (2008, 2009), Israel (2008), Alberta (2015), Canada (2018), Indonesia (2021)
D: Industrial Opposition	Taiwan (2006, 2014, 2020), Korea (2012)
E: Responding to Fiscal Pressure	Ireland (2007), France (2013), Iceland (2013), Portugal (2014), United Kingdom (2015), Spain (2015)
F: Research Gaps	Norway (1991), Netherlands (1992), United States (1993), Australia (1994), Italy (1999), Switzerland (2000), Ukraine (2011), Washington (2016), Germany (2019), Malaysia (2021)

In a similar vein, Mohammadzadeh Valencia et al. (2024) in their analysis for Deliverable 5.3, conducted a meta-analysis of 70 survey studies from 26 countries to examine how different revenue recycling options influence public acceptance of carbon pricing. The analysis shows that public support increases significantly when revenues are directed toward green spending, such as renewable energy investments. In contrast, commonly proposed mechanisms like uniform cash transfers or reductions in income taxes show limited or no consistent effect on support levels. The

study also finds that support for carbon pricing with recycling is particularly strong in Latin America, Africa, and Asia, indicating the importance of local context in policy design and communication strategies.

Discussion on entry points

The studies on Latin America, the Caribbean, and comparative policy adoption globally show that carbon pricing cannot succeed as a purely technical instrument; it must be embedded in broader fiscal and political bargains. Two strategic entry points emerge. First, revenue recycling with social protection is essential to counteract regressive impacts and build legitimacy among vulnerable groups. Second, coalition building and strategic framing—linking carbon pricing to co-benefits such as health, jobs, or fiscal reform—are decisive for adoption and durability. Taken together, these findings suggest that carbon pricing is politically viable when it is designed as a socially responsive and strategically framed policy package rather than a narrow climate instrument.

5. Equity Gaps in G7 International Public Finance for Energy

In this section, we discuss a case study on international energy finance governance and energy transitions. Jaiswal and Chatterjee (2025) examine the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) and the parallel G7 pledge to end new direct international public finance for unabated fossil fuel energy projects and redirect support to clean energy. Using transaction-level data from the Public Finance for Energy database (2017–2023) and Global Energy Monitor infrastructure data, the analysis tracks trends before and after the 2022 commitment across G7 members (Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, UK, US). Recipient countries are grouped by World Bank income classification, and patterns of fossil fuel versus clean energy financing are assessed against domestic fossil infrastructure expansion.

The findings show that while G7 fossil fuel finance fell significantly post-commitment, it did not end and rebounded in 2023, with reductions not matched by proportional increases in clean energy investment. Both fossil and clean energy finance remains heavily concentrated in high- and upper-middle-income countries, while low-income countries received no fossil fuel finance in 2023 and just 0.1% of G7 clean energy flows, mostly as loans. Simultaneously, G7 countries continue expanding domestic oil, gas, and LNG infrastructure, often justifying fossil investments under energy security exemptions, whereas no such exemptions were applied to support development needs in low-income countries.

Jaiswal and Chatterjee (2025) conclude that this “one-size-fits-all” ban risks creating “common but shifted responsibility,” shifting the transition burden onto poorer nations without adequately supporting their clean energy transitions. Policy recommendations include embedding distributive justice into supply-side finance governance and prioritising fossil fuel finance withdrawal in wealthy countries. Further recommendations include ensuring proportional redirection to clean energy in lower-income regions, increasing grant-based support, and aligning domestic actions with international commitments to preserve legitimacy and equity in global climate policy.

International public finance by G7 Signatories for fossil fuels and clean energy by income group of destination countries (2017-2023)

Figure 3. International public finance for fossil fuels and clean energy provided by G7 countries by income groups of destination country

Discussion on entry points

The analysis of G7 commitments and the Clean Energy Transition Partnership demonstrates that restricting fossil finance without expanding equitable clean energy support risks undermining the legitimacy of international climate governance. The key entry point here is equity-focused reform of international public finance, which requires scaling concessional flows, embedding principles of common but differentiated responsibilities, and aligning donor countries’ domestic actions with their international commitments.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable shows that effective climate policy is not only about technology or economics – it must be designed for real-world political and institutional contexts. Sectoral entry points are most effective when grounded in the political economy realities of the places they aim to transform. This deliverable provides both the analytical tools and the empirical evidence to support that approach.

Across the seven studies, three insights stand out:

First, context matters – National and subnational political economies shape what is politically feasible. Second, equity builds legitimacy. Addressing inequality and historical responsibility increases public and political support. Third, integration is essential: Climate goals must be aligned with employment, industrial policy, and fiscal strategies.

The evidence points to five strategic entry points for just, politically feasible, and development-compatible transitions that can be derived from the three areas of work presented in the deliverable:

- Decentralised just transition planning and clean industrial development policies (derived from coal transition strategies)
- Socially targeted revenue recycling; strategic framing and coalition building (derived from carbon pricing and fiscal reform)
- Scaling and targeting concessional flows to low-income countries (derived from international finance governance reform).

By applying the Actors–Objectives–Context framework, the report clusters countries with similar political economy characteristics and illustrates these dynamics through case studies in India and Indonesia, as well as comparative analyses of carbon pricing. This creates a comparative evidence base that can inform tailored transition strategies.

A key outcome is the groundwork for stylised political economy indicators—measures of institutional capacity, fiscal space, actor influence, and public support—that can be embedded into integrated assessment models. Incorporating these parameters will allow scenario modelling that reflects both unconstrained mitigation pathways and the political or institutional barriers that often slow policy adoption. Equally, it will highlight where targeted interventions can accelerate transitions.

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Appendix

For ease of access, the papers referenced below on which this deliverable is based are uploaded on ELEVATE Project's online repository. (Insert Link)

- Jaiswal, Sreeja, and Juhi Chatterjee. 2025. 'Shifting Geographies of Decarbonisation: Gas for Me but Not for Thee'. *Global Environmental Politics* Accepted (Nov 2025 Special Issue).
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